

Developing guidelines in blogging as a writing assessment

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Abstract

Academic blogs give a decent environment for literacy cycles of different sorts. However, since teachers are new to this kind of platform. There is still no available rubric nor guideline in assessing academic blogs, the way teachers use blogs in English language classes and how do teachers use blogs as a writing assessment. With this research, it is hoped that the researchers can develop a guideline for academic blogging as a writing assessment to provide evidence that a guideline can help teachers to have a basis in creating a systematic lesson plan leading to better develop the writing skills of the students. The researcher utilized the qualitative research method as research design. The researcher also utilized thematic analysis to interpret the given data by 20 teacher respondents. The findings show that most of the teacher respondents have been using blogs in their English classes and seem to identify guidelines in giving blogging as a writing activity. However, most of the teachers do not follow guidelines appropriate to the practice of evaluating "blogging," which involves online considerations. Since the researchers assume that most teachers have no specific guidelines in using blog as a writing assessment method, the researchers therefore, formulate a guideline that will serve as a reference for the teachers in using blog to effectively evaluate the writing skills of the students. The researchers believe that this guideline is an essential assessment tool that all teachers should have, especially during the time of pandemic, when most teachers ask students to write, research, and publish their work online.

Keywords: Guidelines; Blogging; Writing assessment.

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Introduction

With the rise of technology in the 21st century education, the modern-day classroom teachers are expected to possess pedagogical competence and performance. They must employ teaching strategies that cater the individual differences of the students. The emergence of complex yet user-friendly technologies that encourage student learning and enable teachers to reinforce learning concepts has fostered innovations in teaching approaches. In a press release from the Department of Education (2021), in the era of technology and digitalization, Dr. Ethel Agnes Pascua-Valenzuela, the Southeast Asian Ministers of Education Organization (SEAMEO) secretariat director, encouraged the education sector to maximize all of these innovations in technology to help each other find solutions being faced in the present situation.

The teaching of English, particularly writing, must therefore be interactive in order to make it more interesting and meaningful for the students in light of the global prevalence of technology. The Web's features make it an effective instructional tool for writing. Teachers can now use social networking sites like Facebook, Instagram, Blogger, and Tumblr as platforms to improve their students' writing abilities, but Blogger is one of these websites that is most frequently utilized in writing classes. Students who participate in blogging can set up their own blog sites where they can publish their essays, poems, as well as other creative works chronologically backwards, with the most recent entry appearing first (Noytim, 2010). That is why Campbell (2003) defines a weblog (or 'blog') "as an online journal that an individual can continuously update with his or her own words, ideas, and thoughts through software that enables one to easily do so."

With this shift in pedagogical patterns, blogging slowly gains popularity among other platforms being used as a learning tool. This innovation is alluded to by many educators as the "digital revolution" stands out (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2016). Since teachers integrate technology in education, blogging nowadays has been utilized in teaching since it has a weblog that keeps sections of blogs that work well for the instructive purposes that can be sorted and provide innovative exercises through correspondence. Most online websites have mechanical means that might be coordinated in a multi-perspective way as an approach to utilize blogging in the teaching and learning process. Blogs having interactive multimedia features support teaching and learning since it provides data and experiences of the blogger. Indeed, blogging has radically changed how individuals communicate online. Users are becoming creators of information instead of just consumers (Stanley, 2013).

Additionally, blogs have recently drawn a lot of attention from both instructors and students as a different method of teaching writing in the classrooms. The blog serves as a good platform for highlighting students' writing mechanics, empowering them, and providing them with more prominent scholarly writing components. A great way for students to communicate with one another in a social situation through innovation is by blogging.

What is good about utilizing blogs in writing classes is that they present the utilization of outside school rehearsals of literacy (Burnett et al., 2014). As indicated by sociocultural hypothesis, education is as a socially based practice and is intervened by a person's way of life (Larson & Marsh, 2015). On the other hand, blogging tends to be upgraded through discourse, conversation, and narrating. This makes self-articulation and assists understudies with talking about their thoughts and afterward sets them up as a written record either independently, two by two, or in a gathering. In this sense, contributing to a blog essentially is not innovation; rather, it is education, which underscores the qualities of valid composition.

Furthermore, blogging additionally gives learners an individual purpose that makes writing more captivating than the academic critical thinking received by most educational plans. Academic blogs give a decent environment for literacy cycles of different sorts, for example, basic reasoning, reflection, addressing, demonstrating, social practices, conversation and advancement, when instructors embrace it for classroom practices. Writing academic blogs is viewed as a muddled undertaking by understudies and their appraisal is additionally a difficult cycle for instructors. Interestingly, the issues in evaluating composing are accepted to outnumber the arrangements.

However, since teachers are new to this kind of platform. There is still no available rubric nor guideline in assessing academic blogs, the way teachers use blogs in English language classes and how do teachers use blogs as a writing assessment. Because of this, teachers utilize a traditional scoring rubric that assesses different talk and linguistic highlights along with explicit principles of academic writing.

With this research, it is hoped that the researchers can develop a guideline for academic blogging as a writing assessment to provide evidence that a guideline can help teachers to have a basis in creating a systematic lesson plan leading to better develop the writing skills of the students.

Methodology

Research Design

The design of the study is qualitative design specifically the basic of generic qualitative study. According to Merriam and Tisdell (2015), for qualitative research study, when selecting a study design, which correlates with the question is imperative. Several types of qualitative research designs are used as fundamental frameworks to conduct studies. Persons' lived experiences may become phenomena (Merriam, 2008) with phenomenologists emphasizing on participants' shared experiences through the gathering of data and personal experiences of a phenomena to a general description that includes all individuals' perspectives (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Another form commonly used in qualitative research, and which was used in this study is case study which is an in-depth study of a group, community, person, or event (McLeod, 2019).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The respondents were randomly taken. This study accommodated 20 teachers of Grade 11 and 12 as respondents, who are willing to provide responses via online data gathering.

Procedure

The study observed a systematic approach of analysis, by following four different phases:

Phase I: Construct and validate the interview questionnaire.

Phase II: Interview the English teachers.

Phase III: Transcribe the recorded interview.

Phase IV: Analyze the data.

Phase I.

The researcher started by constructing an interview questionnaire to get the story behind the teachers' existing practices in terms of integrating "blogging" as a writing assessment, and how these practices affect the students' writing performances. The research questions were then validated by English teachers who are teaching writing.

Phase II.

Bernard (2017) states that data gathering plays a vital role in any research for the reason that the data will contribute to a better understanding of the study. The researcher provided personal data sheet to obtain the basic information of the respondents particularly their name, age, gender, and years of service and experience. The researcher utilized survey questionnaires which were given through Google Forms. The questionnaire solicited information about teachers approach and strategies in giving academic blog as one of their writing assessment tools.

Phase III.

The notes recorded from the interview questionnaires were then transcribed to ensure preservation of data for further and better analysis (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). Through note-taking the researcher was able to demonstrate a "stronger conceptual understanding and were more successful in applying and integrating the material compared to those who took notes with their laptops" (Roller & Lavrakas, 2018). The recorded notes were encoded verbatim, which is frequently used in research as a data management approach and is usually regarded as fundamental to the analysis and interpretation of data (Halcomb, 2006).

Phase IV.

Credible qualitative research requires data analysis to be conducted. It is frequently stated in qualitative research that the researcher's capacity to comprehend, articulate, and interpret viewpoints and experiences serves as the research instrument (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). In analyzing the responses of the participants, the researcher employed a thematic analysis, which is used to find patterns or themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Braun and Clarke gives the following steps, which may not be necessarily linear. Particularly when dealing with complex data, the researcher frequently switches back and forth between them.

Step 1. Become familiar with the data. The researchers re-read the transcript and extracted the important concepts needed in the study.

Step 2. General initial codes. After the first step, the researchers had some initial thoughts on coding. Every passage of text that appeared to be significant to or particularly answer the research questions was coded by the researchers as they went through each transcript. The codes were then compared and altered before the remainder of the transcript. The researchers went through hard copy of the transcripts using pens and highlighters, doing this manually or by hand.

Step 3. Search for themes. The researchers can now search for patterns that reflect anything important or engaging about the research problem. There was a lot of overlap between this step of selecting preliminary themes and the stage of coding because the study only collected minimal amounts of information from a small number of participants. When the researchers looked at the codes in this example, some of them evidently formed a theme.

Step 4. Review themes. The researchers updated and expanded the initial themes found in the third step. Since every piece of data makes sense, the researcher compiled all the information pertaining to each theme. This was done through a 'cut and paste' function in the Microsoft Word processing.

Step 5. Define themes. Identifying the "essence" of each theme is the goal of this final iteration of the themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Step 6. Write-up. This is the output of the research, which is explained further in the last chapters of the paper.

Ethical Consideration

Through a consent form, the researchers informed the participant on what will be discussed about the research. All the information gathered will be solely used for the research study only, and all the information given by the participants will be handled with confidentiality.

Data Analysis and Research Findings

Research Question 1: What are the existing practices of the teachers in terms of integrating "blogging" as a writing assessment?

The findings are presented in the form of themes. As the participants shared the existing practices in integrating blogging as a writing assessment in their English classes, they also need to grapple with the challenges coming within their own external environment.

Theme 1: To check students' knowledge on mechanics

The result shows that majority of the teachers' existing practices in integrating blogging as a writing assessment is to check students' knowledge on mechanics (20%). These are the grammar, vocabulary, punctuation, capitalization, spelling, and others. Most of the teachers say that they find essay writing effective because it targets both vocabulary and grammar of the students; they can check how students use words correctly; it can help students become aware and selective in using correct words; and to improve their vocabulary and grammar.

Theme 2: To check how students follow proper citation to avoid plagiarism

With equal number of responses, most of the teachers' existing practices in integrating blogging are checking how students follow proper citation to avoid plagiarism (20%). Teachers say that the first enemy is plagiarism, so they give blogging to develop students' originality; it is a reliable task to check problems in plagiarism; their objective is to assess students' creation of blog that is free from plagiarism; and to check students' honesty.

Theme 3: To monitor if the students are learning during the course

Other teachers' purpose of integrating blogging is to monitor if the students are learning during the course (15%). They say they integrate blogging to effectively measure students' understanding of the lesson or the topic as a non-objective type of assessment.

They use it as a form of formative assessment and they can say that the students have improvements in their writing ability. Furthermore, it is a good form of formative assessment to help students develop their skills in writing.

Theme 4: To let students express their emotion or ideas freely

Theme 5: To check if students can write original output

Theme 6: To evaluate if students have learned after the course

There are teachers, who integrate blogging to let students express their emotion or ideas freely (10%), to check if students can write original output (10%), evaluate if students have learned after the course (10%).

Theme 7: To check the content or knowledge about the topic

Theme 8: To ask students to write with no specific and clear objective

Theme 9: To check if the students observe online safety

The others integrate blogging to train students how to organize ideas that fits for the content of their blogs (5%); and others say that Blogging develops how innovative students are (5%); and other say I use blogging as an assessment tool on how students share information in the social media (5%).

Table 1. Existing practices of the teachers in terms of integrating "Blogging" as a writing assessment

Memo	Coded Data	Theme
A1	I find essay writing effective because it targets both vocabulary and grammar of the students.	Check students' knowledge on mechanics (grammar, vocabulary, punctuation, capitalization, spelling)
A2	Teachers can check how students use words correctly.	
A3	To help students become aware and selective in using correct words.	
A4	To improve their vocabulary and grammar.	
A5	To train students how to organize ideas that fits for the content of their blogs.	Check the content or knowledge about the topic
A6	Blogging develops how innovative students are.	Ask students to write with no specific and clear objective
A7	To let students express their different perspectives.	Let students express their emotion or ideas freely
A8	To make students learn to express themselves in a creative way.	
A9	It helps the students to be independent and creative in many ways especially in writing.	Check if students can write original output
A10	I can say blogging is somehow reliable since I can easily tell if the output is copied or it is original composition.	
A11	To introduce new way of learning.	Evaluate if students have learned after the course
A12	Let your students unleash their creativity in using blogs.	
A13	To effectively measuring students' understanding of the lesson or the topic as a non-objective type of assessment.	Monitor if the students are learning during the course
A14	I use it as a form of formative assessment and I can say that the students have improvements in their writing ability.	
A15	It is a good form of formative assessment to help students develop their skills in writing.	
A16	I use blogging as an assessment tool on how students share information in the social media.	Check if the students observe online safety
A17	First enemy is plagiarism, so I give blogging to develop students' originality.	Check how students follow proper citation to avoid plagiarism
A18	It is a reliable task to check problems in plagiarism.	
A19	My objective is to assess students' creation of blog that's free from plagiarism.	
A20	To check students' honesty.	

Research Question No. 2: How do these practices affect the students' writing performances?

Table 2. Existing practices that affect the students' writing performances

Memo	Coded Data	Theme
B1	Makes them more confident knowing that their blog will be read not just by their teacher and classmates.	It develops the students' confidence, creativity, and innovativeness
B2	Somehow help them to write with confidence.	
B3	They become innovative and creative.	
B4	They are more aware on the use of words.	Vocabulary skills
B5	They become accurate in using words and conscious on what to write.	Independence
B6	They become more lenient in using different word phrases.	
B7	More aggressive in learning new words since vocabulary is also part of the rubric.	
B8	It makes them more creative and independent.	Editing skills
B9	They learn how to be independent and conscious as well.	
B10	They are sensible enough to learn what are their mistakes and correct it on their own.	Organization
B11	They are concerned in the way they are writing.	
B12	They become conscious and aware of the grammar lapses.	Honesty
B13	More organized and able to create more firm sentences.	
B14	Develops the learners' honesty in writing their own work specially that the information in the internet is easily available.	
B15	In today's world of Industrial Revolution 4.0 this is an exemplification of their 21st century learner's technological skills.	Technological skills
B16	Students are encouraged to publish their work online.	
B17	It helps us to know how the students convey their ideas in writing.	Thinking skills
B18	It helps them to be more creative and productive.	
B19	It develops students' originality of the content.	Originality, writing citation properly, avoiding plagiarism
B20	Becomes aware of the possibility of plagiarism.	

However, Table 2 shows how the existing blogging practices affect the students' writing performances. It can be gleaned that the existing blogging practices mostly develop significant writing skills of the students, which further supports the evaluation process of the teachers.

Theme 1: It develops students' vocabulary skills

Based on the result given by the teachers, it shows that majority of the students develop their vocabulary skills through blogging (20%). The teachers say that students are more aware on the use of words; they become accurate in using words and conscious on what to write; they become more lenient in using different word phrases; and more aggressive in learning new words since vocabulary is also part of the rubric.

Theme 2: Blogging can develop students' confidence, creativity, and innovativeness

Other teachers also believe that blogging can develop students' confidence, creativity, and innovativeness (15%). Teachers believe that blogging makes them more confident knowing that their blog will be read not just by their teacher and classmates; it somehow helps them to write with confidence; and they become innovative and creative.

Theme 3: Students learn how to organize their thoughts into sentences

With the same percentage (15%), other teachers think that through blogging, students are able to organize the load of information in their minds into coherent sentences. Teachers say that students are concerned in the way they are writing; they become conscious and aware of the grammar lapses; and students become more organized and able to create more firm sentences.

Theme 4: Blogging builds students' independence

Theme 5: Blogging builds students' skills in technology

Theme 6: Blogging builds students' thinking skills

Theme 7: Blogging develop students' sense of originality, writing citation properly, avoiding plagiarism

Themes 4, 5, 6, and 7 have the same percentages (10%), where teachers believe that blogging builds students' Independence, teachers say that Blogging makes them more creative and independent; and they learn how to be independent and conscious as well. Other teachers can also observe Students are encouraged to publish their work online; because in today's world of Industrial Revolution 4.0, this is an exemplification of their 21st century learner's technological skills. Through blogging, other teachers can also notice that students become aware of the possibility of plagiarism; it develops students' originality of the content; and it helps them to be more creative and productive. Also, it helps the teachers to know how the students convey their ideas in writing.

Theme 8: Blogging develops students' editing skills

Theme 9: Blogging values honesty

With the same percentage (5%), other teachers believe that blogging makes students sensible enough to learn what are their mistakes and correct it on their own, which develops their editing skills; and it can be noted that blogging also develop students' honesty which is a significant value that students should observe every time they write online, the teacher believes that blogging develops the learners' honesty in writing their own work specially that the information in the internet is easily available.

Discussion

Based from the result of the findings, it can be concluded that most teachers integrate a blogging activity to practice the convention of evaluating the basic rules of the written language or the mechanics like grammar, vocabulary, punctuation, spelling, and others. Doing this measures a student's knowledge of the elements of writing teachers have taught them (Burke, 2009). This agrees with Allen and Huon (2003), who argue that effective writing requires a sound understanding of the mechanics of good writing. Online or not, the mechanics of writing is indeed the most important, because it leads to convey a clear message for the readers to achieve successful communication (MacMillan, 2017).

In other cases, the teacher respondents just wanted to evaluate students' knowledge about the given topic. These topics can be the lesson topic of the teacher or the assigned topic to students, which are usually assessed through essay questions. Essay questions are common when teachers give a question and students create their own response rather than just selecting from given options. Giving an essay question through blogging is actually a good writing assessment because it does not only develop the mechanics of writing, but also other important skills like thinking skills, organization skills, originality, honesty, and other skills identified by the teacher respondents. Through essay questions that can be done through blogging, the teachers provide students the chance to display their critical thinking and reasoning abilities, which gives them the opportunity to recognize any issues that students may be having with their thinking process. Teachers can assist pupils in solving thinking issues when they are identified (Reiner, 2002).

It shows that most of the teacher respondents have been using blogs in their English classes. Blogs can really be great educational tools for all teachers, regardless of subject they are teaching, because students have complete freedom to produce content online thanks to blogs. However, the findings also show that most teachers do not know how to effectively implement blogging into their classrooms, as most of them use blogging without specific or clear objective. This kind of practice may only as good as wadded up balls of paper in the trash as argued by Pappas (2013). These existing practices of the teachers seem to efficiently develop the writing skills of the students as how most teachers commonly practice in their writing classes (Ciampa & Gallagher, 2015).

However, most of the teachers do not follow specific guidelines appropriate to the practice of evaluating "blogging," which involves online considerations and code of ethics especially the use of social media. In the higher education at St. Dominic College of Asia, students cannot just easily visit any websites, which includes blog sites. Most sites are blocked, and teachers still need to send a request to the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) office to allow students to access a particular website. With this policy, it can also explain why there is no existing guidelines for the students and teachers to regulate the use of websites, which includes blog sites.

Since the researchers assume that most teachers have no specific guidelines in using blog as a writing assessment method, the researchers therefore, formulate a guideline that will serve as a reference for the teachers in using blog to effectively evaluate the writing skills of the students. The researchers believe that this guideline is an essential assessment tool that all teachers should have, especially during the time of pandemic, when most teachers ask students to write, research, and publish their work online. As stated by Brown and Lee (2015), guidelines as part of the continuous evaluation implies that there should always be preparation for revision of all the elements in writing. He points out the importance of guidelines and states that *"without guidelines, there is no cohesion among the elements and if left in isolation, any of them may become pointless."*

Conclusion

The findings show that majority of the teachers integrate "Blogging" as a writing assessment in class to check students' knowledge on mechanics (grammar, vocabulary, punctuation, capitalization, spelling) (20%); and check how students follow proper citation to avoid plagiarism (20%). Meanwhile, other teachers use blogging to evaluate if students have learned after the course (15%). With other teachers, they aim that students express their emotion or ideas freely; to check if students can write original output; and to evaluate if students have learned after the course; which are all 10% respectively. Also, other teachers use blogging to check the content or knowledge about the topic; to ask students to write with no specific and clear objective; to check if the students observe online safety; which are all 5% respectively.

Results also show that the existing practices of most teachers affect the writing performances of the students. Majority of the teachers believe that blogging develops the students' skills in vocabulary (20%). Others believe that blogging develops the students' confidence, creativity and innovativeness; and students learn how to organize their thoughts into sentences; which are 15% respectively. With the same percentage of 10%, blogging can build students' Independence; thinking skills; can build students' skills in technology; and can develop students' sense of originality, writing citation properly, and avoiding plagiarism. However, other teachers notice that blogging also develops students' editing skills; and values honesty; which are all 5% respectively.

There is a need to propose a guideline to lead the teachers in practicing blogging that will provide the boundary between classroom writing and blogging. In any institutions or establishments, guidelines are very essential. Guidelines are imperative for any online institution or community. With guidelines, students will know what is expected of them and what types of practices are accepted or not within the community. On the part of the teacher, this guideline will serve as a reference tool that they can always refer to whenever they are unsure about the use of blogging as a writing assessment tool (Hill, 2013).

Recommendations

Therefore, based on the result of the findings and conclusions presented, the following guidelines are recommended:

Guidelines on using Blog as a Writing Assessment

Pre-writing

1. Before even starting an outline of a blogging lesson, the teacher can check with his or her school for a written guideline. From here, the teacher can create clear goals, guidelines, and expectations for him/her and the students. This guideline is usually found in the student / school handbook. If the guideline is not available, this guideline can be used as a reference.
2. The teacher may start off by writing his or her own blog post. It would be more realistic and effective to teach blogging if the teacher has a blogging experience to share. Otherwise, the teacher can start with a classroom blog with just one topic, where students can write their posts under teacher's supervision.

3. The teacher may share actual blogs or written articles posted in different blog sites. This may entice or give a certain reason for students to write their own blogs. The teacher may have this as a spring board discussion to prepare the mindset of the students in writing.
4. The teacher will establish the difference between classroom writing and blogging. Observing the elements of writing in both writing platforms can be the same, but since the content will be published online, there are things that need to be considered, just like the Code of Ethics that follows.
5. What makes blogging unique with classroom writing is that Blogging requires knowledge about the Code of Ethics that students need to be reminded.

Student Code of Ethics Using Blog

1. Students who access or use blogs or other social media platforms must avoid posting any private information. Without written consent from parents, students will not post or distribute pictures of themselves online. Students will refrain from posting any information that would allow someone to find or get in touch with them personally, including their family name, password, user name, email address, home address, school name, city, and country.
2. Students using blogs will treat this tool as a classroom space. Blog posts should not contain language that is unsuitable for the classroom. Students are taught to respect other people's opinions and those of others online.
3. Blog assignments are much like any other type of assignment. Students are expected to follow all rules and regulations in the Student/Parent Handbook while working on the assignment, including those that address plagiarism and proper technology use.
4. Student expression is encouraged in student blogs. They are, however, primarily a tool for learning.
5. Students are not allowed to harass, discriminate against, or endanger the safety of others online. Students must notify a teacher and refrain from responding if they see comments on a blog or other in-class technology that are offensive or make them feel uncomfortable.
6. Students are not permitted to download or upload any software or material when using school equipment to visit blogs or official school websites.
7. Students should be truthful, fair, and trustworthy in obtaining, understanding, and sharing information for the benefit of others. Always cite your sources and check the authenticity of any material.
8. Students shall treat all individuals—including information providers, subjects, sources, peers, and information consumers—with respect. Information should never be gathered and shared in a way that would be detrimental to anyone or any group of individuals.
9. Students must answer to their colleagues as well as their readers, listeners, and viewers. Admit your shortcomings and quickly fix them. Disclose others' immoral information and behavior.
10. Failure to abide by this Code of Ethics may result in academic penalties and/or disciplinary measures in accordance with the Parent / Student Handbook.

During Writing

1. The writing process in the classroom still applies. However, since the content will be published online, the teacher will first ask the students to write a draft about the given writing assignment.
2. In revising the draft, the teacher may teach the students about the proofreading marks. These proofreading marks are marks that teachers write or draw during editing, and students should know how to correct the proofreading marks. Once revised, the student should wait for the teacher's approval before posting. Only approved output should be published as blogs.
3. The teacher may also suggest specific blogging platforms, where students can publish their work (e.g., WordPress, Edublog, Wix, Medium).
4. Once the written articles are posted as blogs, the teachers should monitor the content, and the comments. The teacher should be an active observer of the writing progress of the students. The instructor may motivate students to make insightful comments while prohibiting insults and vulgar language. The teacher can also ask or assign older or well-performing students to manage and monitor blogs or mediate comment sections to help them navigate the world of blogging. These students' roles can be in rotation.
5. The teacher should always be ready to address issues that may arise once the blogs are published particularly, with the issue of cyberbullying.

Post-Writing

1. The teacher should read all the students' blog content and evaluate according to the established rubric. The online blogging rubric may not always be appropriate to evaluate students' blogging because most of them are generic or can be used for evaluating writing in general. So it is better to create own rubric specific to academic blogging only. If a rubric is not available, the rubric that the researchers created can be used (see Appendix A).
2. The teacher should use a plagiarism checker (e.g., Grammarly, Turnitin) to check possible plagiarized content, and if the paper needs immediate editing. The teacher can decide if the work falls inside the appropriate standard percentage level. They can determine whether or not a given piece is duplicated based on the similarities (Business Case Studies, 2019).
3. Make sure to give feedback to the students' writing process. Students may receive feedback, process it, and apply it to grow as writers. There are more options for editing, modification, and future development that a student can receive a feedback on a piece of work. Students' writing will get better the more they write.

For the future researchers, the researchers recommend using the proposed guideline and make a study that can contribute on having more specific and reliable guidelines or rubrics that will help teachers use blogs as an effective writing assessment tool.

References

- Ahluwalia, G., Gupta, D., & Aggarwal, D. (2011). The use of blogs in English language learning: A study of student perceptions. *Profile: Issues in Teachers' Professional Development*, 13(2), 29-41. <https://revistas.unal.edu.co/index.php/profile/article/view/25629/36843>
- Allen, B., & Huon, G. (2003). *The mechanics of writing*. University of New South Wales.
- Bernard, H. R. (2017). *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches* (6th ed.). Rowman & Littlefield Publishers.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Brown, H. D., & Lee, H. (2015). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy* (4th ed.). Pearson Education ESL.
- Burke, J. (2009). *The teacher's essential guide series: Content area writing*. Scholastic Teaching Resources.
- Burnett, C., Merchant, G., Pahl, K., & Rowsell, J. (2014). The (im) materiality of literacy: The significance of subjectivity to new literacies research. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*, 35(1), 90-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01596306.2012.739469>
- Business Case Studies. (2019, September 27). Benefits of using a plagiarism checker. <https://businesscasestudies.co.uk/benefits-of-using-a-plagiarism-checker/>
- Campbell, A. P. (2003). Weblogs for use with ESL classes. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 9(2). <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Campbell-Weblogs.html>
- Cequena, M., & Salle, D. (2013). Does blogging facilitate the development of students' writing skills. *Philippine ESL Journal*, 10, 126-147.
- Ciampa, K., & Gallagher, T. L. (2015). Blogging to enhance in-service teachers' professional learning and development during collaborative inquiry. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 63, 883-913. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-015-9404-7>
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Department of Education. (2021, July 21). Briones recognizes SEAMEO INNOTECH's contribution on PH education on 51st anniversary. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2021/07/21/briones-recognizes-seameo-innotechs-contribution-on-ph-education-on-51st-anniversary/>
- Hill, U. (2013, September 27). *The importance of having a style guide*. Writers Write. <https://www.writerswrite.co.za/the-importance-of-a-style-guide-part-1/>
- Kaplan, A. M., & Haenlein, M. (2016). Higher education and the digital revolution: About MOOCs, SPOCs, social media, and the Cookie Monster. *Business Horizons*, 59(4), 441-450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2016.03.008>
- Marsh, J., & Larson, J. (2015). *Making literacy real: Theories and practices for learning and teaching* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications Ltd.
- MacMillan, G. (2017, February 4). *The importance of mechanics of writing*. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-grammar-punctuation-spelling-gregg-macmillan>
- Maguire, M., & Delahunt, B. (2017). Doing a thematic analysis: A practical, step-by-step guide for learning and teaching scholars. *All Ireland Journal of Higher Education*, 9(3), 335. <https://ojs.aishe.org/index.php/aishe-j/article/view/335/553>
- McLeod, S. (2019). *What's the difference between qualitative and quantitative research?* Simply Psychology. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/qualitative-quantitative.html>
- Merriam, S. B. (2008). Adult learning theory for the twenty-first century. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 2008(119), 93-98. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.309>
- Merriam, S. B., & Tisdell, E. B. (2015). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation* (4th ed.). Jossey-Bass.
- Noytim, U. (2010). Weblogs enhancing EFL students' English language learning. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), 1127-1132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2010.03.159>
- Pappas, C. (2013, September 26). *How to use blogs in the classroom*. eLearning Industry. <https://elearningindustry.com/how-to-use-blogs-in-the-classroom>
- Reiner, C. M., Bothell, T. W., Sudweeks, R. R., & Wood, B. (2002). *Preparing effective essay questions: A self-directed workbook for educators*. New Forums Press. <https://testing.byu.edu/handbooks/WritingEffectiveEssayQuestions.pdf>
- Roller, M. R., & Lavrakas, P. J. (2018). A total quality framework approach to sharing qualitative research data: Comment on Dubois et al. (2018). *Qualitative Psychology*, 5(3), 394-401. <https://doi.org/10.1037/qup0000081>
- Shahzad, M., Asim, T., & Hassan, A. (2021). Impact of different variables on academic performance & learning. *Social Sciences, Humanities and Education Journal (SHE Journal)*, 2(2), 112-131. <http://doi.org/10.25273/she.v2i2.9230>
- Stanley, G. (2013). *Language learning with technology: Ideas for integrating technology in the classroom*. Cambridge University Press.

Appendix
Appendix A. Rubric for Evaluating Students' Blogs

Criteria	Unsatisfactory (70%)	Limited (80%)	Proficient (90%)	Exemplary (90%)
Content and Creativity	Postings show no evidence of insight, understanding, or reflective thought about the topic.	Postings provide minimal insight, understanding, and reflective thought about the topic.	Postings provide moderate insight, understanding, and reflective thought about the topic.	Postings provide comprehensive insight, and reflective thought about the topic by building a focused argument around a specific issue.
Code of Ethics	There are 5 and more ethical guidelines missed in the Code of Ethics.	There are 3-4 ethical guidelines missed in the Code of Ethics.	There is 1-2 ethical guidelines missed in the Code of Ethics.	All the ethical guidelines stipulated in the Code of Ethics were followed.
Citations, Multimedia Elements	No images, media or text created by others display appropriate copyright permissions and do not include accurate, properly formatted citations.	Some of the images, media or text created by others does not display appropriate copyright permissions and does not include accurate, properly formatted citations.	Most images, media or text created by others display appropriate copyright permissions and accurate, properly formatted citations.	All images, media and text used by students display appropriate copyright permissions and accurate citations
Quality of Writing and Proofreading	Written responses contain numerous grammatical, spelling or punctuation errors. The style of writing does not facilitate effective communication.	Written responses include some grammatical, spelling or punctuation errors that distract the reader.	Written responses are mostly free of grammatical, spelling or punctuation errors. The style of writing generally facilitates communication.	Written responses are completely free of grammatical, spelling or punctuation errors. The style of writing facilitates communication.
Appropriateness	There are 3 or more words that are not appropriate for the target audience, the appearance does not reflect the theme of the content like the layout, color palette, logo, etc.	There are 1-2 words that are not appropriate for the target audience, the appearance somehow reflects the theme of the content like the layout, color palette, logo, etc.	The language used is appropriate for the target audience, the appearance reflects the theme of the content like the layout, color palette, logo, etc.	The language used is most appropriate for the target audience, the appearance reflects the theme of the content like the layout, color palette, logo, etc.
Timeliness and Tags	Does not update blog within the required time frame.	Updates blog when reminded; posts are often missing a date stamp.	Updates blog when required; most posts are date-stamped with the most current posting listed at the top.	Updates blog as often, all posts are date-stamped, and categorized correctly. Many also have tags. The most recent posts are placed at the top of the page.